

THE EXPERIENCES AND CHALLENGES OF STUDENTS WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENTS IN SPECIAL EDUCATION (SPED) CENTER, JOLO, SULU

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ABSTRACT

Hearing Impairment (HI) is classified as an invisible disability due to its lack of physical manifestation, making it distinct from other visible disabilities. In the United States, approximately 233,648 deaf or hard-of-hearing students are placed in general education settings without individualized education programs (IEPs), resulting in significant accessibility challenges (National Association of the Deaf). The study aims to explore the difficulties and experiences of students with hearing impairments in basic education, specifically focusing on the challenges faced by the students in Special Education (SPED). This study uses a phenomenological design to explore the experiences of students with hearing impairments in SPED programs at Jolo, Sulu. Ten participants aged 14 to 31 will be purposively sampled. Data will be collected through simplified, open-ended interviews to capture personal insights. Ethical protocols, including anonymized responses and consent, will ensure confidentiality, with data securely stored for research purposes. This study highlights the challenges faced by deaf students in SPED programs, including academic obstacles, emotional struggles, and social exclusion. Despite these difficulties, students demonstrate resilience through adaptive strategies like sign language apps and peer support. The findings call for inclusive practices to foster equity and supportive learning environments. This study examines the challenges faced by students with hearing impairments in the SPED Center in Jolo, Sulu, focusing on academic, emotional, and social aspects. Communication barriers, lack of resources, and insufficient accommodations hinder their education, while stigma and isolation affect emotional well-being.

Keywords: *Academic, Well-Being, Participation, Challenges, Experiences, Hearing-Impairments*

INTRODUCTION

Hearing Impairment (HI) is classified as an invisible disability due its lack of physical manifestation, in contrast to other forms of hearing impairments such as visual or physical impairments, which are more readily discernible (Kigotho, 2016). Globally, the World Health Organization reports that over 360 million individuals worldwide are affected by disabling hearing loss. Within increasing life expectancy, the prevalence of hearing loss has also risen. Nearly one-third of individuals aged 65 and older experience hearing loss.

The National Association of the Deaf reports that around 233,648 deaf or hard of hearing students in the United States are placed in general education classrooms without the support of an individualized Education Program (IEP), which negatively impacts the quality of accessibility and fails to address their specific learning needs effectively. Students with Hearing Impairments (HI) significantly affects and engage with educational content, posing challenges in communication, language development, and academic achievement. Additionally, (Hung & Paul, 2006) stated that background deafness is a common neural sensory impairment that causes feelings of withdrawal, decreased social activities and lower life quality.

Amka and Mirnawati (2020), investigated the social participation in inclusive higher education at Lambung Mangkurat University, involving 5 deaf students and 23 hearing peers. They used quantitative surveys, interviews, and documentation to measure friendships, peer acceptance, and self-perception.

As of a 2020 estimated by the Philippine Statistics Authority, the Philippines is home to approximately 1,784,690 individuals who are deaf of hard of hearing. Despite the significant size of this population, the country faces substantial gaps in deaf education, resulting in many individuals being undereducated and unemployed. However, Special Education (SpEd) programs and services cater to the needs of learners with hearing impairments by offering tailored academic interventions, curriculum modifications, resource support, career guidance, and counseling. These initiatives also include transition programs designed to develop technical-vocational skills and special interest competencies. Additionally, addressing the health and medical needs of students is integral to SPED services, facilitated through schools' referral systems to medical and allied service providers. The success of these services relies heavily on robust collaboration between schools, parents, families, local government units, and various nongovernment and civic organizations.

This study aims to investigate the experiences of students with hearing impairments in Jolo, Sulu Special Education (SPED) addressing the significant disparities and challenges they face. Despite their rights, students with hearing impairments

encounter barriers to inclusive education, healthcare, and social participation. This research will inform policy makers and educational authorities about needs of students with hearing impairments in Special education (SPED) in Jolo, Sulu, leading to more inclusive policies and practices. This can automatically improve the quality of education and promote social inclusion and equity. This research seeks to raise awareness and support for children with hearing impairments, promoting equal opportunities and inclusive education. The purpose of this study is to explore the difficulties and experiences of students with hearing impairments in basic education, specifically focusing on the challenges faced by the students in Special Education (SPED). This study explores on the experiences of students with hearing impairments. Examining their academic, emotional and social challenges within the context of basic education settings. Specifically, it focuses on the students aged of 14-31 enrolled in Special Education (SPED). The study is limited to students with hearing impairments in Jolo, Sulu and does not include those from other regions. The experiences of students are examined within the confines of the SPED program, excluding mainstream educational settings.

Current research on the experiences and challenges of students with hearing impairments primarily focuses on higher education institutions in more developed regions. Studies highlight the general difficulties these students face, such as inadequate resources, insufficient accommodations, and the need for advocacy and self-reliance (Al-Adra, 2016; Al-Fetni, 2021). However, there is a lack of research examining the specific experiences and challenges faced by students with hearing impairments in Special Education programs in Jolo, Sulu. The existing studies do not account for the unique socio-economic and cultural factors that influence the educational experiences of these students. By addressing these gaps, our study aims to provide a deeper understanding of the specific needs and challenges faced by students with hearing impairments in Jolo, Sulu. This will contribute to a more nuanced and comprehensive body of knowledge.

Research Questions

The education of students with hearing impairments is a crucial issue that demands attention. Despite laws and policies, many still face barriers in accessing quality education. In the Philippines, students with hearing impairments in Special Education programs, like those in Jolo, Sulu, encounter challenges affecting their academic success and social inclusion. Research shows they are more likely to have poor academic outcomes, be socially isolated, and have limited post-secondary and employment opportunities. There is a gap in literature on the experiences of students with hearing impairments in the Philippines. This study aimed to fill that gap by exploring the experiences and challenges of such students in Jolo, Sulu. It sought to understand the barriers they face in accessing quality education and identify strategies for promoting inclusivity and improving academic outcomes. By doing so, it hopes to contribute to better policies and practices for their education and inclusion in the Philippines. This sought to answer the following questions:

1. What challenges do students with hearing impairments encounter in their academic challenges?

2. How do students with hearing impairments navigate emotional challenges and promotes their well-being
3. How do students with hearing impairments participate in social participation in social intersection within academic performances?

METHODOLOGY

This proposed study employed a structured phenomenological research design to examine the experiences and challenges of students with hearing impairments on special education (SPED). This approach is selected to allow to provide a deep understanding of the challenges and triumphs of students with hearing impairments. Researchers used a phenomenological design to examine the experiences and challenges of students with Hearing Impairments on Special Education (SPED) center.

The research was conducted at the Special Education (SPED) Center in Jolo, Sulu. This site was chosen specifically because of its rich diversity among students with hearing impairments. This unique setting offers a comprehensive view of different disabilities, which includes the Hearing Impairments (HI), Intellectual Disability (ID), Down Syndrome (DS) and autism spectrum disorder (ASD).

The study aimed to involve six participants from the SPED center, ranging in age from fourteen (the youngest) to thirty-one (the oldest). Participants will be selected through purposive sampling to ensure representation across various academic programs. This careful selection process seeks to include a wide spectrum of experiences and perspectives, thereby enhancing the comprehensiveness and applicability of the research findings.

Data was gathered through a series of open-ended questions directly posed to students with hearing impairments at the SPED center. Due to the researcher's lack of proficiency in sign language, the participant's teacher facilitated communication during interviews with hearing-impaired (HI) students. A simplified written interview guide was utilized. The teacher conveyed the question through sign language, interpret the students' signed responses, and relayed them to the researchers.

The study sought ethical approval from the officials from Special Education (SPED) center. Participants will be informed of the study's purpose, and written consent will be obtained from the head of SPED. All response was treated with utmost confidentiality.

Data collection was scheduled to take place over the course of one week using prepared interview questions conducted through face-to-face written interviews. For participants with hearing impairments (HI), their teacher facilitated the process and assisted in writing down their responses. All collected data will be stored securely and will only be accessible to the members of the research group.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students with Hearing Impairments and their Academic Challenges

Deaf students face significant academic challenges, primarily due to communication barriers and the lack of accessible learning materials. Many participants expressed difficulty in understanding lessons, especially when teachers did not use sign language or visual aids. The absence of real-time interpretation made it difficult for students to grasp complex topics, leading to frustration and slower academic progress.

Additionally, completing assignments was challenging when resource was not available in accessible formats. *Student often relied on their classmates and sign language applications to bridge communication gaps. These applications proved to be valuable tools in improving learning and comprehension.* Furthermore, several participants reported difficulties in completing homework at home due to limited support from family members, particularly parents who were unable to assist with the educational content. This lack of academic support in the home environment contributed to their learning challenges.

Learning new things is tough, especially from books. (P1, Excerpt 3)

I have a hard time learning because I often feel sick. (P2, Excerpt 2)

Studying every day is difficult, especially in math. (P3, Excerpt 1)

Studying is difficult, but I think about signing (sign language) to help me learn. (P4, Excerpt 3)

I find it hard to understand my studies. (P5, Excerpt 3)

I find it hard to stay focused in class. (P3, Excerpt 1)

More books on Filipino Sign Language would be helpful. (P6, Excerpt 5)

I have difficulty when my head hurts. (P5, Excerpt 3)

Reading books is very difficult for me. (P1, Excerpt 3)

I find it hard to understand my studies. (P5, Excerpt 1)

Based on the participants, the challenges faced by them are multifaceted, intertwining academic, social, and emotional aspects of their educational experience. Communication barriers in lecture-based learning and the scarcity of tailored learning resources further exacerbate these difficulties. Without accessible materials, students may miss critical supplementary resources, hindering their ability to reinforce and deepen their understanding of academic content (Aich, 2023).

My friend showed me how to read, which helped a lot. (P1, Excerpt 4)

I get help from friends with English. (P1, Excerpt 5)

I need more support with schoolwork to improve. (P1, Excerpt 6)

Talking with others helps me feel better. (P3, Excerpt 6)

I enjoy meeting friends and classmates. (P1, Excerpt 12)

Despite these challenges, participants demonstrated resilience by seeking assistance from peers, teachers, and employing tools such as sign language applications.

Addressing these academic hurdles requires inclusive practices and targeted accommodations. Real-time transcription services, access to sign language interpreters, and customized learning materials are essential strategies for fostering a supportive and equitable learning environment (Aich, 2023). Such interventions ensure that students with hearing impairments have the opportunity to excel in their academic pursuits.

Students with Hearing Impairments Navigate Emotional Challenges and Promote their Well Being:

Emotional well-being of deaf student faces a unique challenge. Some of them have self-awareness by knowing their limits, by accepting their disability and that it leads to them to have self-confidence to communicate with their peers and educators but in other perception sometimes negative life experiences can sometimes be accompanied by maladaptive behavior such as substance and resilience and a positive sense of well-being can help to mitigate adverse life events.

Additionally, having too much things around them makes them feel weak because of being lack of communication they cannot seek for help sometimes and also some of them can make things easy because of what they were being set in their mindset that people around them can also help them. It was also observed that during the initial stages of the data collection process, some deaf students showed hesitancy and reluctance to participate in interviews. This appeared to stem from a fear of being misunderstood or judged, reflecting their emotional sensitivity and the potential social stigma they face. However, as trust and comfort developed between the researchers and the students, they became more open and willing to share their experiences.

I feel normal when I talk, but why do people gossip about me? (P1, Excerpt 6)

I want people to respect me. (P1, Excerpt 7)

I worry when people gossip about me. (P3, Excerpt 6)

Gossiping should stop. We need to respect all deaf students. (P5, Excerpt 6)

Based on their response, they were not able to participate sufficiently in school activities and extracurricular events because they may have low self-esteem, lack of understanding of social nuances and may not have access to interpreting services after school hours (Byrne & McNamee 2022). Found that communication barriers and lack of easily available support services might cause social disengagement, decreased activity involvement, and feelings of loneliness.

Background deafness is a common neural-sensory impairment which leads to lower life quality, withdrawal, social activities reduction, and rejection feeling. so, it is important to plan suitable training programs for mental health promotion of deaf children.

Furthermore, Crowe (2022) compared 206 Deaf adults (ASL users) and a matched sample of hearing adults to examine how negative life experiences, substance use

patterns, well-being, and resilience differ between the groups. Data were collected via surveys assessing trauma exposure, substance behaviors, and psychological outcomes.

My first teacher made me happy. (P1, Excerpt 8)

I learn by listening to my teachers. (P2, Excerpt 9)

I am happy when I talk and stay with my friends. (P5, Excerpt 7)

My mother tells me to stay in school and not go out too much. (P5, Excerpt 8)

I feel safe when people understand me. (P6, Excerpt 8)

Despite these challenges, they still manage to communicate give their best to understand everyone around them and if things make hard for them to understand they seek help to teacher and also, they use app (Iglesia Ni Cristo sign language) to know some words they were being unfamiliar with and watched videos to help them seek knowledge.

Social Intersection and Participation of students with Hearing Impairments:

A deaf person is someone who has a deficiency in or loss of hearing ability, either partly or wholly, so that they cannot use their hearing in daily life, which seriously impacts all aspects of their lives. The implementation of inclusive education enables special needs children, including the deaf, to access education services that suits their needs.

When I ask questions, people sometimes get angry. (P1, Excerpt 12)

Communication is difficult when we lack understanding. (P2, Excerpt 13)

If I feel left out, I walk away and go home. (P6, Excerpt 11)

Sometimes, I don't understand how group work is done. (P6, Excerpt 13)

I try to stay calm and happy by talking with my friends. (P3, Excerpt 7)

According to their response, they often face unique experiences and challenges in their areas. While social engagement is critical for all students, the particular difficulties that students with hearing impairments frequently encounter, such as communication barriers, accessibility issues, may limit their ability to participate fully in both academic and extracurricular activities. Collaboration between professionals, such as speech and language pathologists and deaf pedagogues, plays a crucial role in ensuring that students with hearing impairments receive the necessary support. Furthermore, the role of language in social interaction cannot be overlooked. Language serves as the primary medium through which people connect, express themselves, and build relationships. As such, the extent to which sign language is incorporated into the school environment directly impacts the social and cognitive development of students with hearing impairments, ultimately influencing their educational achievements (Mosia, 2021).

Sarkar and Ghosh (2024) explored the multifaceted challenges experienced by students with hearing impairment in higher education. Through a comprehensive review of research and policy data, they highlighted communication barriers, social inclusion issues, limited academic resources, and the psychological impacts associated with stigma and isolation.

If my classmates and I are busy with schoolwork, we finish tasks quickly so we can go home and rest. (P2, Excerpt 12)

I like talking about food, gadgets, and other topics with my friends. (P6, Excerpt 12)

I have classmates who help me study. (P1, Excerpt 1)

I like to talking with my seatmate. (P4, Excerpt 12)

I like meeting new classmates. (P5, Excerpt 12)

Additionally, being actively involved in their environment plays a crucial role in making individuals, particularly those with hearing impairments, feel comfortable and connected. When they engage with their surroundings—through meaningful interactions with peers, supportive relationships with teachers, or participation in group activities—they develop a stronger sense of belonging. This fosters not only emotional comfort but also enhances their ability to adapt socially. Social adaptation involves the individual's adapting to the external environment by changing the environment or oneself. It is an important way for individuals to integrate into social life, improve social status, and realize their life value. (Hong et al. [2023](#)),

Conclusions

This study explored the academic, emotional, and social experiences of students with hearing impairments enrolled in the Special Education (SPED) Center in Jolo, Sulu. The findings revealed that these students face multifaceted challenges that impact their educational outcomes, emotional well-being, and social participation. Communication barriers, lack of accessible resources, and limited accommodations hinder their academic progress. Emotionally, students often experience feelings of isolation and low self-esteem due to stigmatization and inadequate support systems. Socially, difficulties in forming relationships and participating in group activities further exacerbate their sense of exclusion.

Despite these challenges, students demonstrated resilience by utilizing adaptive strategies such as sign language applications, peer support, and seeking help from teachers. These efforts highlight their determination to overcome barriers and succeed academically and socially. The study underscores the importance of inclusive practices, such as providing tailored learning materials, real-time interpretation services, and fostering supportive environments that promote social integration.

The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the unique needs of students with hearing impairments in SPED programs within socio-economically and culturally distinct settings like Jolo, Sulu. This research emphasizes the need for policymakers and educators to prioritize inclusive education policies and interventions that address these challenges. Future studies should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of specific accommodations and interventions designed to enhance academic performance, emotional well-being, and social participation among students with hearing impairments.

By addressing these gaps, this study aims to promote equity in education and ensure that students with hearing impairments receive the support they need to thrive academically, emotionally, and socially.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several key recommendations are proposed to improve the academic, emotional, and social experiences of deaf students within inclusive educational settings.

Research Agenda/Policy

1. Academic Support and Inclusive Teaching Strategies

Deaf students face considerable academic challenges primarily due to communication barriers and the lack of accessible resources. It is recommended that Teachers should be trained in inclusive teaching strategies that incorporate visual aids, sign-supported speech, and other multimodal approaches to enhance comprehension. The adaptation of learning materials into accessible formats—such as captioned videos, visual presentations, and interactive sign language applications—is essential. Furthermore, the implementation of real-time transcription tools can significantly improve academic access and participation.

2. Emotional and Mental Health Intervention

The emotional well-being of deaf students must be prioritized, as it directly affects their motivation and academic performance. Schools should establish safe and inclusive spaces where students can freely express themselves. Regular counseling services, in collaboration with trained interpreters, should be provided to address emotional concerns and promote mental health. Awareness campaigns focused on anti-bullying, respect, and empathy for students with disabilities should be regularly implemented. Additionally, peer mentorship programs can foster a stronger sense of belonging and emotional support.

3. Social Inclusion and Participation

Participation in social and extracurricular activities plays a vital role in the development of deaf students. To ensure inclusive engagement, schools must organize events and group tasks that provide appropriate communication support. Collaborative activities should be designed to promote interaction between deaf and hearing students. The involvement of professionals such as sign language interpreters, speech and language therapists, and special education specialists is crucial in supporting social adaptation and integration.

4. Policy and Institutional Support

Institutions should develop and enforce inclusive education policies that support the academic and social development of students with disabilities. Adequate funding should be allocated to recruit qualified interpreters and develop accessible learning resources. Furthermore, schools are encouraged to build partnerships with organizations that support the deaf community in order to provide comprehensive assistance and advocacy.

5. Family and Parental Involvement

Parental support is a critical component of student development. However, findings reveal that some students experience a lack of understanding and communication with their parents. Therefore, parents should be encouraged to learn basic sign language to strengthen their communication with their children. Parenting seminars and training workshops should be provided to help families understand the unique needs of deaf learners. Regular parent-teacher meetings, with the assistance of interpreters, should be conducted to foster consistent collaboration between families and educators. Such initiatives can empower parents to support their children's educational journey more effectively

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All participants signed an informed consent form before taking part in the study. This study also ensured full confidentiality and anonymity. Ethical approval was obtained from the school head and class advisers and other research committee.

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REFERENCES

- Aich DK. Educational Challenges of Students with Hearing Impairment in India. *Educ. Soc. Econ Disadvantaged Groups*; c2023 Jan 31. p. 101-112. 1
- Al- Fetni, S. (2021). Curricular for teaching people with hearing impairments in light of modern
- Al-Adra, I. (2016). Challenges facing students with hearing impairments at the University of Jordan: a field study. *Dirasat - Humanities and Social Sciences*, 43, 2013-2032.

- Amka, A. (2020). Social participation of deaf students within inclusive higher education. *Social Participation of Deaf Students within Inclusive Higher Education*, 11.
- Byrne, B., & McNamee, C. (2022). The emotional well-being of deaf children and young people in Northern Ireland. Queen's University Belfast.
- Crowe, T. (2022). Negative Life Experiences, Substance Use, Well-Being, and Resilience: A Comparison of Deaf and Hearing Adults. *International Journal on Social and Education Sciences*, 4(3), 391-407.
- Hong, M., & Lv, S. (2024). The current situation and influencing factors of social adaptation of hearing impaired middle school students: a qualitative research. *Current Psychology*, 1-12.
- Kigotho, L. W. (2016). Barriers faced by students with hearing impairment in inclusive learning environment, a case of the University of Nairobi (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi). <https://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/98908>:
- Mosia, M. N. (2021). Challenges of Using Sign Language Interpreting to Facilitate Teaching and Learning for Learners with Hearing Impairment. M.R. Pulatkhodjaeva (2023).
- Sarkar, R., & Ghosh, A. (2024). Challenges faced by students with hearing impairment in higher education: A comprehensive analysis. *International Journal of Speech and Audiology*, 5(1), 06–12. <https://doi.org/10.22271/27103846.2024.v5.i1a.43>